

**THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF MORAL FOUNDATION TOWARDS
MOTIVATION AND PASSION FOR TEACHING AMONG
PUBLIC SCHOOLS TEACHERS: BASES FOR
PROPOSED SUSTAINABILITY PROGRAM**

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The Mediating Effect of Moral Foundation Towards Motivation and Passion for Teaching among Public Schools Teachers: Bases for Proposed Sustainability Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the mediating effect of moral foundation on the relationship between motivation and passion for teaching among public school teachers bases for proposed sustainability program. Using quantitative, non-experimental design via correlational technique, data were obtained from 206 elementary public-school teachers from the three districts of Polomolok 1, Polomolok 4, and Polomolok 5, under the Division of South Cotabato in the province of South Cotabato. The researcher utilized a stratified random sampling technique and an online survey mode of data collection. The researcher also utilized the statistical tools mean, Pearson r, and Medgraph using the Sobel z-test. From the results of the study, it was found that there was a very high level of mean scores for motivation, a very high level of mean score for passion for teaching of teachers, and a very high level of moral foundation of teachers. Also, results revealed significant relationships between the motivation and passion for teaching of teachers, between the motivation and moral foundation of teachers, and between passion and moral foundation of teachers. Further, it revealed that there was a partial mediation effect of moral foundation on the relationship between motivation and passion for teaching of public elementary school teachers.

Keywords: *educational management, motivation, passion for teaching, moral foundation, mediating effect*

Introduction

Teachers are the primary agents who shape the course of any nation. Their performance is determined by their dedication and enthusiasm for the job. Passionate and highly motivated teachers who are sincerely committed to their work might help students succeed in their future endeavors. Also, teachers' understanding and opinions on moral education considerably influence children's character development. Passion can significantly motivate learning and teaching by fostering enthusiasm and action (Fabelico & Afalla, 2020; Gilal et al., 2019). Moreover, teachers who are eager and passionate about their work and dedicated to their student's education influence their student's classroom performance. Passionate teachers understand that their responsibility is to motivate students to engage in active learning while encouraging intellectual and moral development. Furthermore, enthusiasm is required for effective, high-quality teaching. A passionate teacher inspires pupils in a classroom by making learning fun (Ashkani et al., 2021; Khan, 2020; Ruiz-Alfonzo & Leon, 2019). On the other hand, motivation for teaching is essential in affecting the quality of the teaching-learning experience provided because teachers' views, beliefs, and intentions, which are linked to their motivation, impact their classroom behaviors and their students' motivation. Highly motivated instructors have better job engagement, contentment, and productivity (Lan, 2022; Osman & Warner, 2020).

Furthermore, understanding teachers' challenging circumstances and motivations is highly important because these aspects help them serve as effective conduits for students' future accomplishments and success. Teachers are unquestionably important moral role models; students look to them for direction. Consequently, the understanding and viewpoints of teachers and instructors about moral education profoundly impact the formation of pupils' character as it guides them to become better citizens of the nation (Asif et al., 2020; Nilsson et al., 2020). Moreover, by creating and bolstering a range of policies, initiatives, and support networks that will close the achievement gap, the education sector—and, more significantly, the Department of Education (DepEd)—can significantly impact teachers' drive and excitement for their work. Also, more studies are needed to track teachers' motivation and passion. It is critical to underline that the success of DepEd projects is defined by their implementation, communication, and alignment with teacher needs. Continuous feedback systems and coordination among educators and policymakers can help overcome potential hurdles and increase the positive impact of DepEd on teachers' motivation and love for teaching.

Nevertheless, the researcher was interested in learning the mediating effect of moral foundation towards motivation and passion for teaching among public school teachers. In light of the above information, the researcher was interested in determining whether a moral foundation would mediate the relationship between teachers' motivation and passion for teaching public schools. As a result, this study had the potential to generate new knowledge and ideas that would substantially impact the field of education.

Literature Review

Motivation

Teacher motivation is vital to the success of the teaching and learning processes. The study found that motivation theories apply to teacher motivation. Motivating teachers necessitates school leaders to meet critical work-related requirements, both intrinsic and extrinsic. The fulfillment of these demands pushes instructors to improve their performance, as evidenced by learner achievement on standardized national assessments. Desired learner achievement might drive school leaders to consistently address teachers' work-

related demands to excite teachers and maintain increased learner performance (Osman & Warner, 2020; Thommen et al., 2021). Additionally, more than good teaching is needed. The education sector requires 'good teachers' who not only teach well and use good strategies and practices but who also enjoy their work, where 'love' means both 'liking,' gaining a positive effect from working with students and colleagues, and 'managing,' feeling capable and believing in one's ability to overcome the difficulties of teaching. It entails a commitment to students, school, the advancement of their careers, the broadening of their professional knowledge bases, and the teaching profession—teachers who are committed to their students like working with them and are interested in how they grow. Teachers who are passionate about their work motivate their students to participate actively in school-related activities. Additionally, teachers must be committed to giving high-quality instruction (Ruiz-Alfonso & Leon, 2019; Vermote et al., 2020). It has been demonstrated in the existing body of research that motivated educators display higher levels of productivity and demonstrate goal-oriented and persistent actions, particularly when confronted with challenges and adversities. As a result of the fact that teaching motivation is essential for the quality operation of the institution and for enhancing the student's learning experience, it is a topic frequently discussed in discussions about quality assurance methods. Furthermore, examining the intrinsic motivation of higher education instructors is essential for accurately predicting and improving positive teaching behaviors, time commitment, and pedagogical innovation (Jang, 2019; Yasmeeen et al., 2019; Yukhymenko-Lescroart et al., 2019).

Self-efficacy. Bandura (1997) found that a person's belief in their ability to act in a given scenario is influenced by personal and societal qualities, local culture, history, school atmosphere, and job satisfaction. This construct was developed as a result of research conducted on various themes, including but not limited to intellectual insights, attributions of success and failure, goal formulation, problem-solving, professional choice, teaching, and teacher education. A teacher's goals and actions at school are influenced by their beliefs. In addition, values can enhance one's subjective well-being and one's feeling of self-efficacy. Teachers' self-efficacy, or belief in their competence to manage professional tasks, significantly impacts academic outcomes (e.g., student achievement and motivation) and workplace well-being (Barni et al., 2019; Menezes et al., 2020; Yada et al., 2019).

Outcome efficacy. Corresponding to the teachers' ideas, they can control and influence the environment to get the intended outcome if they apply their teaching talents. Personal efficacy refers to teachers' perceptions of their competence as educators. Furthermore, outcome efficacy is related to teachers' view that their behaviors were directly responsible for student results (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2020; Wu et al., 2019). Further, teachers play a crucial role in shaping the educational landscape, and their perceptions of their effectiveness can significantly influence student outcomes. The efficacy of instructor outcomes is directly related to student achievement. When educators are confident in their abilities to begin change, it often results in better pedagogical practices and higher student academic achievement (Hall, 2023; Perera et al., 2019). A teacher's confidence in effectively managing the classroom influences the learning environment. High efficacy is associated with improved classroom management techniques that enhance learning. This is essential for fostering a supportive and inclusive atmosphere for children's intellectual and social development. Educators possessing a robust sense of efficacy are more inclined to implement innovative and effective teaching methodologies. Their confidence motivates them to explore innovative teaching approaches and adjust to their students' needs (Chen, 2019; Valente et al., 2020).

Undeniably, teacher outcome efficacy is strongly related to motivation and job satisfaction. Educators who believe they can make a difference are more likely to be motivated, enthusiastic, and content with their jobs. Teachers with a strong sense of effectiveness are more willing to pursue professional development opportunities. They see these possibilities as ways to improve their abilities and contribute to their students' achievement. Supporting teachers' professional development is critical for sustaining and growing their effectiveness levels (Dörnyei & Ushioda, 2021; Perera & John, 2020; Savolainen & Schwab, 2020).

Teaching efficacy. This pertains to educators' beliefs that their instruction can mitigate the effects of external influences on student achievement; the third factor, teaching efficacy, involves teachers' convictions regarding the influence of external factors, including home environment, heredity, and television violence, on education. Albert's social learning and social cognitive theory define "teacher self-efficacy" as a teacher's belief in his or her abilities to foster student engagement and learning, even when students are challenged or uninspired. Bandura's research reveals that instructors with high levels of self-efficacy are more open to novel teaching approaches, set themselves more ambitious goals, demonstrate a higher degree of preparation and organization, focus their efforts on problem-solving, seek support, and attain (Granger et al., 2023; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2020). In addition, individual instructor self-efficacy demonstrates how the individual teacher's perspectives connect to students' academic advancement; collective teacher efficacy aids in understanding the differential effect of faculty and schools on student outcomes. As a result, a thorough assessment of the effectiveness of approaches for increasing teacher self-efficacy is critical in the classroom. When confronted with a challenge, teachers modify their instructional approach. Self-efficacious instructors are less prone to experience burnout and are happier with their jobs. This also benefits their students, who exhibit improved motivation, academic adjustment, and accomplishment levels (Lazarides & Warner, 2020; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2020).

Interest. Research on teacher motivation has recently focused on interest as a second factor. Individual and situational interests are distinguished within the term 'interest': Personal interests are generally consistent and connected to the inherent worth of a specific activity, whereas situational interests are primarily formed by contextualized factors and, thus, are more related to extrinsic factors of motivation; interests are generally the result of combining an individual disposition, the content of the object of interest, and context characteristics. Interests inspire choices, shape decisions, and participate in action planning to achieve those choices through the decision-making process. In general, interests generate positive emotions and foster a positive atmosphere or ethos (Fachmi et al.,

2021; Zhang et al., 2019).

Teacher interest is multidimensional, encompassing characteristics such as professional development, intrinsic motivation, and a passion for teaching. Ryan and Deci (2000) address intrinsic motivation, highlighting the significance of autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Teachers who find their jobs inherently rewarding are more likely to be motivated and involved in their field. Furthermore, passionate teachers about their subject and the teaching process often show high interest. Teachers are keen to try new and innovative teaching methods that add to the dynamic nature of education (Demir, 2020; Khan, 2020).

Effort. In particular, teachers have a vital influence on the learning process of pupils who idolize them and strive to emulate them. Teacher motivation is, therefore, essential because it directly impacts students. Most instructors were dissatisfied with their incomes, and it was found that low salaries impacted their ability to teach. The majority of instructors were dissatisfied with their current economic situation. They desired to improve their living standard, but they could not do so. Many teachers believed that they were more capable than others. Most teachers agreed that students, rather than teachers, should be held accountable for their poor performance. A few teachers thought teachers should be provided incentives and rewards for good performance (Farid & Alam, 2023; Zou et al., 2024). On the other hand, teachers' motivations for engaging in the profession still need to be examined. The quality of instruction should be more considered in research and policy, resulting in a need for more investment from educators and institutions. Furthermore, research is frequently favored over teaching. Motivation for teaching is a crucial factor in the quality of the learning experience at this level, as teachers' perceptions, beliefs, and intentions, linked to their motivation, affect their classroom behaviors and subsequently influence their students' motivation. Highly motivated educators exhibit elevated levels of job engagement, contentment, and productivity (Bardach & Klassen, 2021; Osman & Warner, 2020).

Passion

Teachers are known for their passion for their subjects and exhibit enthusiasm, intellectual fervor, emotional vitality, and dedication. When interacting with students, they possess a feeling of identity and believe they can influence their learning and success. A passion for teaching enhances comprehension and advancement within the field, along with providing fresh perspectives on the experiences of educators. Instructors' commitment correlates with their professional emotional identity, while the commitment of teachers is linked to their professional emotional identity. The most effective teaching methodologies involve synthesizing emotional and cognitive abilities (Prates et al., 2019; Talapatra et al., 2020). In addition, passion is a driving force, so high-quality learning and teaching is a vast requirement. Passion is seeking out and experiencing new ideas. Passion is built upon effective instruction. Passion, essential for learning and teaching, aids learning through the desire and passion it generates. Passionate teachers strive to maximize their student's learning potential by establishing effective learning environments (Serin, 2020; Yukhymenko-Lescroart & Sharma, 2019).

Passion Criteria. Passion is defined as a deep-seated commitment and enthusiasm towards work that is aligned with personal identity, distinguishing between harmonious and obsessive passion. It outlines criteria for harmonious passion, including positive emotional experiences and voluntary engagement, which have been linked to improved job satisfaction and emotional resilience among teachers. The criteria for assessing passion in educational settings focuses on the impacts of harmonious and obsessive passion. Their research identifies autonomy, identity alignment, and positive engagement as central criteria that distinguish harmonious passion, promoting a sustainable teaching practice and reducing burnout (Bureau et al. 2019; Liu et al., 2020). The dualistic model of passion, particularly the criteria that contribute to harmonious passion, such as autonomous motivation and positive identity integration emphasizes that teachers who possess harmonious passion experience higher job satisfaction and personal well-being compared to those with obsessive passion, who are driven by external pressures and compulsions. The analyzed criteria defining passion among educators, noting that autonomy, value alignment, and self-regulation are key characteristics of harmonious passion. This study suggests that these criteria enable teachers to maintain a balanced approach to their work, enhancing job satisfaction and minimizing stress (Fernet et al., 2020; Phipps et al., 2022).

Harmonious Passion. One factor that measures passion is harmonious passion. Harmonious passions, it was believed, are fostered in environments that support autonomy and intrinsic needs. Individuals in autonomous environments can explore and choose whatever activities are meaningful. Autonomous conditions, on the other hand, can increase intrinsic motivation. Intrinsically motivated people, for example, pursue goals or rewards based on their innate desires and engage in activities only for the pleasure and intrigue they provide. In this case, an individual can develop a balanced excitement for an activity based on fun and fulfillment (Prates et al., 2019; Ruiz-Alfonso & Leon, 2019). People with a harmonious passion should be able to focus on the activity set before them and embrace positive outcomes during and after task engagement in terms of flow, pleasant effect, concentration, satisfaction, and overall positive affect. As a result, there should be little or no conflict between the individual's intense activity and their other everyday activities. Finally, with harmonious passion, the individual can control the action and decide when to participate. People with a harmonious passion can choose not to participate in the activity on a given day if necessary. Alternatively, they can discontinue their connection with the movement if they deem it a constant unpleasant component. Thus, behavioral involvement in a passionate activity may be considered adaptive (Dalla-Rosa & Vianello, 2020; Ramzam et al., 2021; Vallerand et al., 2020).

Obsessive Passion. On the other hand, obsessive passion stems from the controlled integration of an action into one's identity. Individuals with obsessive interests may have an intense urge to engage in meaningful and pleasurable activities. The person's fervor for the action prevails. They are compelled to participate in rigorous activities, resulting in steadfast perseverance (Jang et al., 2023;

Kasprzak & Mudło-Głagolska, 2022; Vallerand et al., 2020). A strong passion can make work more fun. Employees passionate about their jobs are willing to participate in whatever required activities. Passion is associated with learning, caring, and taking action. Passionate education involves emotional, motivational, and scientific skills. Teachers deemed passionate about teaching include emotions, motivation, and knowledge (Ashkani et al., 2021; Horwood, 2021).

Many teachers start the teaching profession with enthusiasm for their jobs, but they must possess the necessary abilities or attributes to be good educators. Some teaching abilities can be improved, but the majority of them must be inherent in order to be an effective educator. Passion is a trait that teachers and students regularly put among the top ten essential talents, and it has been confirmed as one of the most crucial by numerous research investigations. Despite the importance of passion as a teaching attribute, scholars have differing views on the definition of passion and whether it can be taught to individuals entering teaching (Fabelico & Afalla, 2020; Vallerand et al., 2020).

Moral Foundation

Teachers are the epitome of ethics and honesty. In addition to transmitting knowledge, teaching is a comprehensive, moral endeavor that entails developing the morals and character of future generations. Teachers must have a solid moral base to establish a secure and ethical learning environment. Other parts of education may take time to be recognized as morally relevant, yet they can significantly impact students' intellectual and social growth. Such factors could include teachers' relationships with students. Teaching contributes significantly to societal progress. The individual's responsibility to have a close, intimate relationship with others is a fundamental component of morality and ethics in education. This goal allows the teacher to accomplish the intended goal while effectively interacting with students and others (Atari, 2020; Carr, 2023).

Social and cultural psychologists developed the moral foundations theory to explain why morality varies significantly between cultures while exhibiting numerous commonalities and recurring motifs. The idea posits that various innate and universally available psychological systems underpin "intuitive ethics." Each culture then builds virtues, myths, and institutions on top of these foundations, resulting in the distinct moralities we witness worldwide and internal conflicts. The five foundations on which we believe the evidence is most substantial are:

Care/harm. Teachers are recognized for their mothering instincts, so it is no surprise that humans exhibit nurturing and caring behavior even when they are not taught how. Negative moral emotions and beliefs are automatically aroused by behavior that causes suffering in other people, particularly children. In contrast, actions that exhibit genuine care and compassion generate good emotions and beliefs. As previously said, one example of a general trigger for this foundation would be a person preparing to club a newborn seal. An education-specific trigger would be a group of adolescents laughing and pointing to another sad-looking adolescent (Haidt, 2012; Meyer, 2023). Teaching is a holistic ethical activity that fosters future generations' values and character and imparts knowledge. Educators must have a solid moral foundation to create a safe and moral learning environment. Strong empathy and compassion are necessary for the educator's ethical framework. Teachers must teach academics and create a nurturing environment where children feel appreciated and supported. This caring attitude promotes trust and emotional safety, which are necessary for effective learning (Sikes et al., 2003; Soleimani & Lovat, 2019).

Fairness/Reciprocity. People are innately programmed to interact with other people in a "tit-for-tat" fashion: cooperate with those who are trustworthy and shun those who are dishonest. Teachers are role models for virtue and honesty. They maintain these principles when interacting with students, coworkers, and community members. Listening to teachers and seeing how their words and actions align is an excellent way for students to learn from them. The goal of every educator should be to provide every student with an equal opportunity to learn and develop personally and academically. Fighting prejudice and discrimination creates a fair classroom and teaches kids to be good citizens. Teachers are heavily responsible for their students' overall development. This includes academic advancement and the development of critical life skills, social-emotional competence, and ethical decision-making. Teachers know the long-term impact they can have on a student's character (Arifudin & Ali, 2022; Maxwell & Narvaez, 2013).

Loyalty/betrayal. This basis stems from our tribal nature and ability to establish dynamic coalitions. It sits at the heart of patriotism and self-sacrifice for the greater good. It is active when people believe it is "one for all and all for one." Regarding education, loyalty in teaching usually means a commitment to the work, a devotion to students, and an adherence to moral principles. A strong dedication to students' welfare, education, and development is a prerequisite for teacher loyalty. In addition to the fact that teachers with a solid moral foundation are better equipped to make moral decisions in various contexts, this commitment is rooted in a moral foundation of empathy, compassion, and a sense of obligation to influence the lives of the children under their supervision. Loyalty to ethical ideals enables instructors to prioritize the best interests of students, colleagues, and the educational community, especially under challenging circumstances. Certainly, dedication to educational values and principles is inextricably linked to a teacher's moral foundation. Teachers ethically devoted to educational goals such as equity, inclusion, and academic excellence show loyalty by advocating for and implementing these values in their classrooms. Teachers contribute to a positive school culture by adhering to moral standards. This includes creating a secure and supportive learning environment, encouraging courteous relationships, and demonstrating ethical behavior. Loyalty to these core ideas fosters a culture of learning and progress (Doğruyol et al., 2019; Ismail et al., 2022)

Authority/respect. Our primate's lengthy history of hierarchical social interaction shared this foundation. It underpins leadership and

follower characteristics such as respect for legitimate authority and tradition. This foundation is based on honoring one's position within a network of people and the traditions and values of one's culture. The underlying assumption is that traditions and authority persons will preserve societal order. Acts of disobedience and disrespect arouse negative moral emotions and beliefs, whereas good emotions and beliefs are triggered by respect for tradition and authority. This foundation's adaptive challenge is to build positive partnerships inside social hierarchies (Haidt, 2012). The authority and respect teachers command in the classroom are closely tied to their moral foundation. The moral principles and values that guide teachers' actions significantly influence their ability to establish and maintain authority while earning the respect of students and fostering a positive learning environment. Teachers with a solid moral foundation serve as role models for ethical behavior. By consistently demonstrating honesty, integrity, and fairness, they establish a foundation for respect. Students are more inclined to regard and react favorably to teachers who embody the moral principles they seek to instill. Teachers who genuinely care about their students and empathize with their challenges are more likely to earn respect and maintain authority (Burgoon, 2018; Butera, 2021; Shi et al., 2020). Indeed, teachers confronted with ethical quandaries use their moral grounding to make decisions consistent with their ideals. Ethical decision-making increases pupils' trust and respect for their teachers. It strengthens the teacher's power since students understand the teacher's dedication to ethical standards. A moral basis based on open communication and transparency improves teachers' capacity to connect with students. Teachers who stimulate dialogue, actively listen, and communicate effectively establish connections with students, winning their respect and sustaining classroom authority.

Purity/Sanctity: The concept of moral underpinnings, notably purity and sanctity, influences the values and ethical issues in educational environments. The emphasis on moral underpinnings such as purity and sanctity can take several forms in education. Character education efforts frequently seek to teach qualities and ideals in kids. Character education programs can emphasize purity and sanctity, instilling moral responsibility and regard for sacred values (Haidt & Joseph, 2004). Classroom discussions about ethical decision-making may include considerations of purity and sacredness. Teachers may study scenarios in which behaviors align with or contradict these moral foundations, encouraging students to think critically about the ethical consequences of their decisions. In educational environments that recognize diverse cultural and religious backgrounds, teachings on purity and sanctity may be integrated in ways consistent with many belief systems. This promotes an inclusive approach to moral education that values diverse viewpoints. Schools and educational communities may prioritize local beliefs and traditions that incorporate features of purity and sanctity. This might be represented through rituals, ceremonies, or behaviors that emphasize the sacred aspect of education (Calvert, 2021; Haidt & Joseph, 2004; Lindström & Samuelsson, 2022).

Liberty/oppression. This foundation concerns the emotions of reactance and resentment individuals experience towards those who exert dominance and curtail their freedom. Haidt envisioned the Moral Foundations theory as facilitating new approaches to resolving and understanding moral conflicts by recognizing that cultures built their unique moralities on a foundation of shared, universal intuitions (Haidt, 2012). In conclusion, the moral foundation of teaching is a multifaceted commitment to caring, respect, integrity, fairness, responsibility, professional ethics, and the promotion of social and civic engagement. Teachers, as moral agents, wield a profound influence on the ethical development of their students. By embracing and embodying these moral principles, educators contribute to academic success and cultivate compassionate, responsible, and ethical individuals prepared to navigate the world's complexities (Maxwell & Narvaez, 2013; Oleksiyenko & Jackson, 2020).

Correlation between Measures

Moral foundations, motivation, and passion for teaching are deeply intertwined. Moral foundations refer to the underlying ethical principles that guide an individual's values, such as care, fairness, or loyalty. These principles often influence motivation, the internal drive that pushes someone to take action, like the desire to help others or contribute to society. In teaching, moral foundations can inspire a teacher's commitment to fostering growth, equity, and empathy in their students. Passion for teaching often emerges from this combination of moral beliefs and motivation. When a teacher is driven by strong moral values—such as a belief in the importance of education for all—they are more likely to invest deeply in their work, go beyond mere job duties, and feel a sense of purpose. In turn, their passion can enhance their ability to motivate and inspire students, creating a positive cycle where both teacher and students are energized by shared values and goals (Grillo & Kier, 2021; Zhang et al., 2019).

Correlation between Motivation and Passion for Teaching

According to studies, the most common conceptualizations of passion are dedication, tenacity, identification with, and affection for the activity. Passion study in education indicated various outcomes, such as engagement, creativity, the subject's election or mastery goals, and a variety of promoters, such as positive relationships, a supportive environment, or an inventive cognitive style. Understanding passion is vital in helping pupils adjust and learn. Passion for teaching is regarded as vital for quality learning (Fogelgarn & Burns, 2020; Vallerand et al., 2020). Also, teacher's motivation has been highlighted as one of the most important factors influencing the future performance of education and institutions. Teacher motivation is intimately related to teachers' work performance and ability to innovate and incorporate new ideas into their practice, as well as absenteeism and staff turnover. An individual's passion for teaching is crucial to their commitment and involvement with the profession (Khan, 2020; Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2020). Moreover, the level of teachers' commitment is crucial to the success of the present educational reform agenda because it determines their desire to engage in cooperative, reflective, and critical practice. Devoted teachers have been observed to be excited, passionate, driven, enthusiastic, and energetic. Teachers' dedication to teaching and learning will allow them to create something new, ever-changing, and authentic. As

previously stated, instructors are passionate about their profession and will continually strive for further knowledge and learning because they enjoy what they do, resulting in enhanced teaching effectiveness. Despite its challenges, teaching is a challenging vocation that requires dedication, enthusiasm, and passion. Teachers must also be motivated and devoted to accomplishing their long-term goals to positively impact their students' lives (Fabelico & Afalla, 2020; Siddique et al., 2023).

Furthermore, it was believed that dedication to teaching is an effective way to improve teaching practice. Teachers committed to education are responsible for exploring new teaching techniques to enhance students' learning experiences. Teachers who are dedicated to their profession have the potential to teach pupils new teaching practices that can lead to improved achievement (Grillo & Kier, 2021; Zhang et al., 2019). Moreover, a motivated teacher is constantly looking for new ways to help their kids and is always dissatisfied with their current situation. A motivated educator will be excited about teaching and studying. As previously stated, when a teacher grows, so do students' academic achievement and personal development. Such a teacher is capable of generating authentic learning and practical education. As a result, learning and teaching processes will be automatically facilitated, enhancing both teachers' and learners' potential (Gilal et al., 2019; Meriç & Erdem, 2020).

Furthermore, one of the most essential components in creating a passion for teaching is teachers' commitment to their students and their education. Teachers who are enthusiastic about their profession might inspire and stimulate their students' desire to study. It has been said that the power of a profession is measured by the dedication of those who practice it, which is valid for teaching. It was emphasized that teachers' passion stands out and positively impacts student advancement. Lifelong learning is a passion and commitment that only highly motivated teachers can fulfill. Teaching truly is a complete endeavor. It is a noble career. The teacher is responsible for a tremendous task. Several authors found a correlation between teachers' passion for teaching and student accomplishment (Daniel & Sapó, 2020; Medina-Carls, 2020; Miguel et al., 2019).

Correlation between Motivation and Moral Foundation

Individuals with higher intrinsic motivation tend to display stronger moral foundations, such as fairness and care. Individuals driven by personal fulfillment and a desire for growth are more likely to adhere to moral standards, as intrinsic motivation aligns with internalized moral values. Also, motivation influences the endorsement of different moral foundations, showing that individuals with higher intrinsic motivation are more likely to support moral foundations such as care, fairness, and harm prevention. The findings suggest that intrinsic motivation fosters a sense of empathy and social responsibility, which enhances moral development (Krettenauer et al., 2020; Prentice et al., 2019). Certainly, employees with a strong sense of moral responsibility, driven by prosocial motivation, tend to prioritize moral foundations related to fairness, loyalty, and integrity. The findings highlight that moral foundation and motivation are intertwined, especially in work environments requiring ethical decision-making. Individuals with high moral motivation are likely to engage with moral foundations that prioritize care, fairness, and loyalty. Research shows that people motivated by ethical values align with moral principles, suggesting that moral motivation can play a critical role in upholding and promoting ethical behavior (Graham et al., 2022; Winterich et al., 2021).

Correlation between Moral Foundation and Passion for Teaching

Teachers' passion for teaching is influenced by moral foundations such as care, fairness, and loyalty. The study found that teachers with a strong sense of moral purpose, driven by intrinsic moral values, are more likely to experience harmonious passion for teaching. This intrinsic alignment between passion and moral foundation encourages teachers to engage more meaningfully in their work, benefiting both educators and students. Research indicates that teachers with high moral foundations, particularly related to care and fairness, tend to demonstrate greater resilience and harmonious passion for teaching. They concluded that a teacher's moral commitment to the well-being of students fosters a more enduring and positive passion for teaching (Gore et al., 2019; Mansfield et al., 2020). Moreover, teachers who view teaching as a moral endeavor experience higher levels of intrinsic motivation and harmonious passion, which positively impacts their instructional effectiveness and engagement with students. Teachers' moral foundations influence their sense of purpose and passion. Teacher who prioritize moral values related to loyalty and care are more likely to develop a deep, harmonious passion for teaching, which leads to positive classroom environments and enhanced student-teacher relationships (Hansen & Guttormsen, 2022; Zhu et al., 2021). Teachers' passion for teaching is shaped by their moral foundation. They found that moral principles such as empathy, responsibility, and social justice contribute to a more resilient and positive passion for teaching. Teachers with a strong moral foundation are more likely to experience harmonious passion, resulting in sustained motivation and professional well-being (Bialystok & Waldman, 2023).

Methodology

This study employed a quantitative non-experimental correlation designed to measure the association between motivation and passion for teaching. Descriptive non-experimental correlational design controlled the degree to which one variable was related to another or more variables. In this study, the correlation method was the best strategy to achieve this study's goals and find out whether the hypothesis was accepted. H_0 was born, and H_a was accepted if the significance value was more significant than .05. The hypothesis testing determined if the correlations could be strong or weak (Creswell, 2012; De Vaus, 2001; Ghanad, 2023; Goertzen, 2017).

In addition, a survey allows the researcher to investigate the traits, habits, and experiences of those who participated in the study

(Calmorin & Calmorin, 2007; Paler-Calmorin & Calmorin, 2007). This study is more descriptive than anything else since it assessed the role of moral foundation, motivation, and passion for teaching teachers. This correlational study explored the relationship between qualities such as moral foundation motivation and passion for teaching. The survey questionnaire was used to acquire the primary data for this study. Investigating the connection between these two things was the primary goal of studying moral foundation and motivation, the relationship between motivation and passion for teaching, the relationship between moral foundation and passion, and the mediating effect of moral foundation on the relationship between motivation and passion for teaching. Zobel z test and medgraph were essential in deciding how the mediation would go (Preacher & Leonardelli, 2001).

This research was conducted at public elementary schools in Polomolok 1, 4, and 5 Districts, Division of South Cotabato. School A and B- 130736, School C- 130720, School D-208509, School E- 130738, School F- 501233, School G- 130741, School H- 130742, School I- 130743, School J- 130745, School K-130734, School L- 130747, School M- 130748, School N- 112750, School O- 130749, School P-130735 and School Q- 130750.

The researcher distributed the study's modified questionnaires via Google Forms to school heads and teachers. The respondents were 425 teachers in the Municipality of Polomolok from Polomolok 1, 4, and 5 Districts, Division of South Cotabato, who completed the modified survey questionnaires. The survey was restricted to permanent public school teachers from the district who were randomly selected to participate. As a result, as mentioned in the study's exclusion criteria, substitute teachers, volunteer teachers, and school staff were excluded from the study. Thus, as stated in the withdrawal criteria in this study, the researcher also considered teachers, who throughout the actual administration of the survey questionnaires, decided to withdraw or back out. Those who withdrew from the study were not penalized.

Furthermore, the respondents were chosen using a purposive sampling technique. Researchers utilized purposeful sampling when they had a specific group of people in mind that they wished to speak with, as all survey respondents were selected based on whether they fit a particular profile (Jordan, 2021). There were 425 elementary teachers in Polomolok 1, 4, and 5 Districts. Slovin's Formula was used to get the desired sample. The researcher used Slovin's Formula ($n=N/1+N e^2$) to get the desired sample from each school population and considered them as official respondents of this study: wherein Bentung Elementary School, the sample size was 13 out of 27; Bentung Elementary School-Annex 1 the sample size was 4 out of 8; Crossing Palkan Elementary School the sample size was 5 out of 10; Eustacio Barcatan Elementary School was 22 out of 46; Glamang Elementary School was 10 out of 2; Klinan Integrated School was nine out 19; Koronadal Proper Elementary School the sample size was 15 out of 31; LR Morandante Integrated School 8 out 16; Lumakil Integrated School the sample size was 7 out of 15; Polomolok Central Elementary School had 57 out of 117; Silway 7 had five out 10; Silway 8 Elementary School had 21 out of 43; Sto. Niño Elementary School had 7 out of 14; Sulit Elementary School the sample size was 4 out of 9; Sumbakil Elementary School the sample size was 4 out of 8; Upper Klinan Elementary School had 9 out of 19; and Viray-Lising Integrated School had 6 out of 12 teachers with a total of two hundred six (206) elementary teachers as sample size.

The researcher used Slovin's Formula ($n=N/1+N e^2$) for the sample size. N was the population size, and the margin of error $e(0.05)$ indicated the permissible likelihood of making an error in selecting a small representative from the population. Moreover, the researcher followed the inclusion and exclusion criteria in which teachers of private schools and Alternative Learning Systems were not included in the administration of the research questionnaires. Besides, the researcher withdrew when it was found that the respondents no longer met the inclusion and exclusion criteria or were considered too distressed or at risk of harm to continue.

Three separate sets of questionnaires were taken from works written by other writers. Specialists then validated these sets of questions in developing questionnaires. The experts' opinions were appropriately taken and incorporated in the finalization of the instrument, as mentioned above. The contents of the adopted standardized questionnaire were reliable because the author had already tested and demonstrated them. Additionally, the questionnaire underwent modification to classify the questions. The questionnaires were created in a very detailed form with the assistance of proficient validators to give convenience and satisfaction to the respondents in responding to every concern and comprehending the purpose of the investigation.

The first part of the questionnaire was utilized to determine the level of motivation selected for use, and subsequent research led to its modification. This variable had five indicators: self-efficacy, interest, effort, teaching efficacy, and outcome efficacy (Bandura & Wessels, 1997). The second part of the questionnaire was used to ascertain the level of passion among public school teachers through the following indicators: Passion Criteria, Harmonious Passion, and Obsessive Passion (Serin, 2020; Yukhymenko-Lescroart & Sharma, 2019). Moreover, the third section of the survey was devoted to the role of moral foundation, including indicators such as care/harm, fairness/reciprocity, in-group/loyalty, authority/respect, and purity/sanctity (Graham et al., 2011; Graham et al., 2013).

A systematic process was used to collect all the pertinent information. Data collection is an organized process of gathering information to answer research questions, test hypotheses, or evaluate outcomes. De Vaus (2001) asserts that this design yields summary statistics, particularly measurements of central tendency encompassing the mean and standard deviation correlations between variables, utilizing analytical methods such as Pearson r, Sobel-z test, and medgraph multiple variable analysis. Correlational studies often employed independent and dependent variables, wherein the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable was observed without manipulation of the independent variable. This technique was appropriate since the study aims to determine whether moral foundation was related to teachers' motivation and passion for teaching (Levitt et al., 2018). This study followed a systematic process. Initially, the

researcher sent a letter of authorization to the Superintendent of the Division of South Cotabato to carry out the study. Moreover, the researcher wrote another letter addressed to the elementary school principals in this study to allow the researcher to survey the teachers in their respective districts. Upon approval, survey questionnaires were administered to the public elementary school teachers in Polomolok 1, 4, and 5 Districts. The researcher created the questionnaires using Google Forms to avoid face-to-face transactions with the respondents due to the restrictions of the COVID-19 pandemic adopting the new normal. Afterwards, the researcher gathered the questionnaires one week after distributing the link to the Google forms so that the respondents had enough time to answer the questions. The questionnaires were distributed using Google Forms and was successfully recovered in a manner equal to one hundred percent of the total. Automatic checks and tallies were performed on the results of the completed work. In the end, following the completion of the automatic tallying of all the results, these were examined and interpreted in light of the study's goals.

The statistical tests used to interpret and analyze the data more comprehensively were as follows:

Mean was applied to establish the level of motivation, passion, and the role of moral foundation to answer research objectives 1, 2 and 3.

Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was carried out to ascertain whether there was a genuinely substantial connection between the passion and motivation of teachers to answer research objective number 4.

Sobel z test and medgraph. These were used to establish if moral foundation significantly mediated the relationship of motivation and passion for teaching among public school teachers to answer research objective number 5.

Results and Discussion

This part presents the analyzed and interpreted data acquired from the respondents on motivation, passion, and moral foundation. The analysis and interpretation were based on the research objectives stated before. The order of discussions on the mentioned topic is as follows: level of motivation; level of passion; moral foundation; correlations between teachers' motivation and passion for teaching; correlations between teachers' motivation and moral foundation; correlations between moral foundation and passion for teaching; and on the mediating effect of moral foundation towards motivation and passion for teaching among public school teachers.

Level of Motivation

The level of motivation is shown in Table 1. The overall mean score was 4.40, labeled very high, with an SD of 4.43. This implies that many teachers were deeply motivated to educate and shape young minds. Their love for teaching and commitment to student growth motivated them to improve and stay engaged continuously. Distinctively, the level of motivation of teachers on the following indicators are as follows: self-efficacy got a mean of 4.35, referred to as very high; interest has a mean of 4.38 with a descriptive level of very high; effort obtained a mean of 4.55 which is interpreted as very high, teaching efficacy garnered a mean of 4.28 with a descriptive level as very high and outcome efficacy has a mean of 4.44 characterized as very high. Conversely, teaching efficacy was the lowest among the five indicators. This meant that some teachers who needed adequate support felt overwhelmed and isolated, thus, diminishing their confidence in their teaching abilities. Moreover, data revealed that teachers dedicated significant energy and effort to fulfill their teaching endeavors. Educators possess sufficient knowledge of the content to teach effectively. Also, the job holds great importance to them; thus, a substantial amount of effort is added to their duties.

Table 1. *Level of Motivation of Public School Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Self-efficacy	0.44	4.35	Very High
Interest	0.62	4.38	Very High
Effort	0.51	4.55	Very High
Teaching Efficacy	0.56	4.28	Very High
Outcome Efficacy	0.53	4.44	Very High
Overall	0.43	4.40	Very High

Level of Passion for Teaching

Table 2 shows the results of the level of Passion of public elementary schools in Polomolok 1, 4, and 5 Districts. The overall mean score was 4.21, labeled very high, with an SD of 0.53. This implies that teachers were deeply committed to their profession and were enthusiastic about helping the learners learn and grow. It involved a genuine love for the subject matter and a desire to impact students' lives positively. Mainly, the level of responsibility on the following indicators are as follows: passion criteria got a mean of 4.42, which is interpreted as very high; harmonious passion has a mean of 4.40 with a descriptive level of very high; and obsessive passion with a mean of 3.82 characterized as high. Furthermore, it was observed that passion criteria and harmonious passion obtained very high ratings, indicating that teaching was a passion for them, and it held great importance in their lives. Teachers with this Passion were often highly motivated, creative, and patient, going above and beyond to engage students, inspire curiosity, and adapt their methods to meet their learners. Moreover, it showed that teachers genuinely enjoyed teaching as it allowed them to have a diverse range of experiences. Also, their job as teachers aligned harmoniously with other aspects of their identity. This Passion has fueled teachers' ongoing professional development and commitment to fostering a friendly and inclusive learning environment.

Table 2. *Level of Passion for Teaching of Public School Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Passion Criteria	0.58	4.42	Very High
Harmonious Passion	0.55	4.40	Very High
Obsessive Passion	0.78	3.82	High
Overall	0.53	4.21	Very High

Level of Moral Foundation

Teachers' moral foundation level was analyzed based on the obtained and computed mean ratings of the indicators: Care/Harm, Fairness/Reciprocity, In-group/Loyalty, Authority/Respect, and Purity/Sanctity of the teachers. It can be gleaned from Table 3 that the moral foundation of teachers garnered a total mean rating of 4.44 or Very High and an SD of 0.47. This implies that teachers with a solid moral foundation model positive values, maintain professionalism, and foster a safe, inclusive, and equitable learning environment. Thus, they are committed to their student's well-being, promoting honesty, empathy, and justice in their teaching practices while being mindful of their role in shaping students' character and values. It can also be seen from the table that the care/harm indicator gained the highest mean score of 4.53 with an SD of 0.57, labeled as Very High. This was followed by purity/sanctity with a mean score of 4.50 with an SD of 0.55, characterized as Very High; fairness/ reciprocity indicator showed a mean score of 4.47 with an SD of 0.56, labeled as Very High; authority/respect garnered a mean of 4.42 with an SD of 0.62. Lastly, the indicators in-group and loyalty gained a mean score of 4.28 with an SD of 0.64, which is interpreted as very high. The table showed the results of the level of moral foundation among public school teachers, which was very high. This means teachers were governed by morally right behaviors in their teaching endeavors. Additionally, a high moral foundation in teachers refers to a robust ethical framework that guides their behavior and decision-making in the classroom and beyond. It means that teachers uphold principles such as integrity, fairness, respect, and responsibility in their interactions with students, colleagues, and the community.

Table 3. *Level of Moral Foundation of Public School Teachers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Care/Harm	0.57	4.53	Very High
Fairness/Reciprocity	0.56	4.47	Very High
In-group/Loyalty	0.64	4.28	Very High
Authority/Respect	0.62	4.42	Very High
Purity/Sanctity	0.55	4.50	Very High
Overall	0.47	4.44	Very High

Significance of the Relationship between Motivation and Passion for Teaching of Public School Teachers

Presented in Table 4 is the correlation between measures of motivation and Passion for the teaching of public school teachers. The table shows that the connection had an overall r-value of 0.813 with a p-value lower than the 0.05 significance level. This indicated a significant relationship between motivation and passion for teaching Public School Teachers. Consequently, the null hypothesis asserting no significant association between motivation and Passion for teaching was rejected. It can also be gleaned from the table that motivation was significantly correlated to the passion for the teaching of teachers since the indicators revealed the following overall R-values: self-efficacy with 0.711, interest with 0.732, effort with 0.575, teaching efficacy with 0.620, outcome efficacy with 0.595; and the p-value is 0.001. Thus, the two variables were significantly associated.

Table 4. *Significance of the Relationship between Motivation and Passion for Teaching of Public School Teachers*

<i>Motivation</i>	<i>Passion for Teaching</i>			<i>Overall</i>
	<i>Passion Criteria</i>	<i>Harmonious Passion</i>	<i>Obsessive Passion</i>	
Self-efficacy	.599**	.694**	.520**	.711**
Interest	.000	.000	.000	.000
	.691**	.740**	.463**	.732**
Effort	.000	.000	.000	.000
	.581**	.626**	.302**	.575**
Teaching Efficacy	.000	.000	.000	.000
	.512**	.558**	.497**	.620**
Outcome Efficacy	.000	.000	.000	.000
	.516**	.633**	.387**	.595**
Overall	.000	.000	.000	.000
	.731**	.817**	.544**	.813**

Further, data also revealed that the passion for teaching teachers was significantly correlated to motivation. The indicators revealed the following overall R-values: passion criteria with 0.731, harmonious Passion with 0.817, obsessive passion with 0.544, and a p-value 0.001. Hence, Passion for teaching and motivation were positively associated. The correlation between motivation and Passion

for teaching revealed a significant relationship. This implied that motivation was significantly correlated with Passion for teaching. Highly motivated teachers were likely to have a more extraordinary passion for teaching, and vice versa. The correlation indicated that these two factors were connected and influenced each other meaningfully.

Significance of the Relationship between Motivation and Moral Foundation of Public School Teachers

Presented in Table 5 is the correlation between Motivation and Moral Foundation of Public School Teachers. It can be seen from the table that when motivation was correlated with the measures of moral foundation, the overall r-value was revealed to be 0.544, and the p-value was 0.001, which was less than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicated a significant relationship between motivation and moral foundation. The null hypothesis positing no significant relationship between motivation and moral foundation was rejected. The data also revealed that moral foundation was positively correlated with motivation as indicated by the overall R-values of the following measures: self-efficacy with 0.381, interest with 0.408, effort with 0.421, teaching efficacy with 0.471, outcome efficacy with 0.477, and p-value with 0.001. Thus, moral foundation and motivation were significantly associated. The association between motivation indicators and instructors' moral foundations was considerable. This implies a positive correlation between motivation and teachers' moral foundation.

Table 5. Significance of the Relationship between Motivation and Moral Foundation of Public School Teachers

Motivation	Moral Foundation					
	Care/Harm	Fairness/Reciprocity	In-Group/Loyalty	Authority/Respect	Purity/Sanctity	Overall
Self-efficacy	.153*	.312**	.392**	.334**	.310**	.381**
	.029	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Interest	.179*	.293**	.388**	.395**	.352**	.408**
	*.010	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Effort	.255*	.344**	.314**	.350**	.413**	.421**
	*.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Teaching Efficacy	.254**	.369**	.526**	.395**	.309**	.471**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Outcome Efficacy	.335*	.366**	.423**	.423**	.338**	.477**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Overall	.297**	.423**	.515**	.480**	.434**	.544**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

Significance of the Relationship between Moral Foundation and Passion for Teaching of Public School Teachers

Table 6 presents the correlation between moral foundation and Passion for teaching public school teachers. The table indicates an overall R-value of 0.537 and a p-value of 0.001 below the 0.05 significance threshold. This indicated a significant correlation between the moral foundation and Passion for teaching public school teachers. Consequently, the null hypothesis asserting no substantial association between moral foundation and Passion for teaching was rejected. Data also revealed that when the Passion for teaching teachers was correlated with moral foundation, the following overall R-values were revealed: passion criteria with 0.425, harmonious Passion with 0.532, obsessive Passion with 0.409, and p-value with 0.001. These indicated that the passion for the teaching teachers and moral foundation were significantly associated. The correlation between the measures of moral foundation and passion for teaching revealed a significant correlation. This implies that passion for teaching was significantly correlated to the moral foundation of teachers.

Table 6. Significance of the Relationship between Moral Foundation and Passion for Teaching of Public School Teachers

Moral Foundation	Passion for Teaching			
	Passion Criteria	Harmonious Passion	Obsessive Passion	Overall
Care/Harm	.265**	.306**	.094	.247**
	.000	.000	.179	.000
Fairness/Reciprocity	.353**	.432**	.306**	.427**
	.000	.000	.000	.000
In-group/Loyalty	.303**	.403**	.567**	.525**
	.000	.000	.000	.000
Authority/Respect	.364**	.502**	.321**	.462**
	.000	.000	.000	.000
Purity/Sanctity	.410**	.466**	.310**	.461**
	.000	.000	.000	.000
Overall	.425**	.532**	.409**	.537**
	.000	.000	.000	.000

Mediation Analysis

Data was submitted to the medgraph after being subjected to a linear regression analysis. The mediation analysis, established by Baron

and Kenny (1986), pertained to the mediating effect of a variable on the correlation between two other variables. Mediation analysis involved four steps for the third variable to be considered as a mediator. Presented in Table 5 are the steps categorized as Steps 1 to 4. Step 1 presents the significant direct effect of motivation on Passion for teaching. In Step 2, motivation significantly affected the moral foundation, the mediator (M).

Meanwhile, Step 3 presents the analysis results, which suggested that a moral foundation significantly predicted motivation to be passionate about teaching. Further mediation analysis using medgraph was necessary to determine the significance of the mediation effect because paths a, b, and c are found to be correlated. This analysis involved the Sobel z test. Full mediation occurs when the analysis indicates that the independent variable has no statistically significant effect on the dependent variable. It implies that the mediator variable is the mediating variable for all effects (Preacher & Leonardelli, 2001).

Table 7. Regression * $p < 0.05$ analysis shows motivation's influence on Passion for teaching as mediated by the moral foundation

Step	Path	B	S.E.	β
1	c	1.014	.051	.813***
2	a	.598	.065	.544***
3	b	.153	.054	.135***
4	c'	.923	.060	.739***

Additionally, when the regression coefficient is significantly reduced on the last step and stays significant, only partial mediation is attained, which suggests that the moral foundation mediates a portion of motivation. At the same time, other components are directly or indirectly influenced by factors not involved in the paradigm. Furthermore, as observed in step 4 (denoted as c'), the influence of motivation on Passion for teaching was even reduced after being mediated by a moral foundation. With this, partial mediation occurred since the effect was significant at $p < 0.05$. Furthermore, the result of the computation of mediating effects is shown in Figure 7. The Sobel test in Table 8 yielded a z-value of 2.703688, $p < 0.05$. This means that the mediating effect was partial, such that the original direct motivation to a passion for teaching was reduced upon adding a moral foundation. The positive value of Sobel Z indicated that adding a moral foundation reduces the effect of motivation on Passion for teaching.

Table 8. Results of statistical analysis on the presence (or absence) of mediating effect

Combination of Variables	Sobel z	p-value	Mediation
motivation → moral foundation → passion for teaching	2.703688	<0.001	Partial mediation

* $p < 0.05$

Additionally, the computed effect size for the mediation test seen between the three variables is shown in the figure. The effect size determines the level of the effect of motivation on Passion or teaching, which can be associated with the indirect path. The total effect value of 1.014 was attributed to the beta of motivation towards passion for teaching. The direct effect value of 0.923 was the beta of motivation towards passion for teaching with a moral foundation included in the regression. The indirect effect value of 0.598 was the value obtained from the original beta between motivation and Passion for teaching that now passes through the moral foundation to Passion for teaching ($a*b$, where "a" denotes the path M → MF and "b" pertains to the the the the path between MF → PFT). The indirect effect was divided by the overall effect to obtain the ratio index; in this case, 0.598 by 1.014 equals 0.5897. About 58.97% of the total effect of motivation on passion for teaching went through moral foundation.

Sustainability Program Based on the Findings of the Study

Our research program collaborates with teachers to enhance their ability to support student autonomy during instruction, thereby improving student motivation and classroom engagement. Our research program collaborates with teachers to enhance their ability to support student autonomy during instruction, thereby improving student motivation and classroom engagement. The following sustainability initiatives are recommended in light of the study's findings. Developing a program to improve teachers' passion necessitates taking care of several of their personal and professional growth areas. Cultivating a passion for teaching among public school teachers was crucial for creating a positive and engaging learning environment. Based on the study's results, a sustainability program was designed to ignite and sustain the Passion for teaching, specifically in terms of obsessive passion, which was found to be the lowest among the many indicators in this study.

Professional Development

- Passion-Driven Teaching Workshops: Conduct workshops focusing on finding and maintaining Passion in teaching. Include sessions on innovative teaching methods and real-world applications.
- Subject-Specific Training: Provide specialized training to help teachers deepen their knowledge in their subject areas.
- Guest Speakers and Role Models: Invite successful educators, community leaders, or experts to share their passion for education.

Curriculum Innovation

- Project-Based Learning Initiatives: Encourage teachers to design and

implement project-based learning experiences. Link projects to real-world issues, fostering a sense of purpose and relevance.

b. Community Engagement Projects: Incorporate community projects into the curriculum, allowing teachers to connect with the community and students to see the impact of their learning.

Recognition and Appreciation

a. Passion-Driven Teacher Awards: Establish awards recognizing teachers who demonstrate exceptional Passion in the classroom.

b. Student Testimonials: Encourage students to share stories about teachers who have inspired them.

Teacher Support Networks

a. Passion Circles: Create small groups where teachers can share their passions and inspirations. Encourage dialogue on integrating Passion pedagogical methods.

b. Peer Observation and Feedback: Implement a system where teachers can observe each other's classes. Provide constructive feedback and encourage the sharing of successful strategies.

Well-being and Work-Life Balance

1. Stress Management Workshops: Offer workshops on stress management and maintaining work-life balance. Emphasize the connection between well-being and sustained passion for teaching.

2. Flexible Professional Development Days: Allow teachers to have flexible professional development days to pursue their interests or attend events aligned with their passions.

Community Involvement

1. Parent-Teacher Collaboration: Establish consistent communication

Channels between educators and parents to foster a collaborative learning environment. Involve parents in classroom activities and projects.

Continuous Feedback and Growth

a. Passion-Driven Professional Goals: Encourage teachers to set professional development goals aligned with their passions. Provide ongoing feedback and support for achieving these goals.

b. Reflective Practices: Promote reflective practices where teachers regularly assess their teaching methods and adjust based on feedback and experiences. Create a culture of continuous improvement.

Celebrating Successes

a. Passion Showcases: Arrange events where teachers can showcase their passion projects to the school community. Celebrate achievements and highlight the positive impact on student learning.

Implementing these initiatives requires collaboration between teachers, school administrators, and the community. Regularly assess the program's impact through surveys, feedback sessions, and student performance indicators to ensure its effectiveness in promoting and sustaining a passion for teaching among public school educators. Implementing these initiatives requires commitment from school administrators, teacher engagement, and ongoing evaluation to ensure the sustained development of an obsessive passion among public school teachers.

Conclusions

Numerous recommendations are proposed based on the findings and conclusions. Firstly, teachers need to intervene in teaching efficacy, which is found to be the lowest indicator of motivation. School administrators may develop an activity that solves teachers' problems related to their difficulties controlling to do the job as a teacher. In this case, schools, especially the school heads, may offer targeted professional development sessions and training to facilitate collaborative learning communities where teachers can share experiences and strategies. Additionally, school administrators may encourage peer observation and feedback to promote a culture of mutual support and growth by establishing mentorship programs pairing experienced teachers with those who have lower self-efficacy. Foster a mentor-mentee relationship that includes regular check-ins, guidance, and encouragement. Acknowledge and celebrate teachers' achievements and successful teaching practices. Provide opportunities for reflective practices, allowing teachers to assess their progress and celebrate successes. Furthermore, they should create a safe space for open communication about self-efficacy concerns. Remember, building and sustaining self-efficacy is an ongoing process. A supportive and collaborative approach is essential, enabling educators to feel empowered and equipped to surmount problems and enhance their teaching techniques consistently.

Secondly, there is also a need for teachers to improve on obsessive passion, which is found to be the lowest indicator of passion. Mitigating obsessive zeal among educators is essential for fostering an excellent work-life equilibrium and averting burnout. Obsessive passion, characterized by an uncontrollable urge to engage in an activity, can negatively affect well-being. School administrators may encourage teachers to establish clear boundaries between work and personal life, thus emphasizing the importance of taking breaks, disconnecting after work hours, and utilizing vacation time. In addition, school heads can provide training on effective time management techniques to help teachers prioritize tasks and manage workload efficiently. Assist educators in seeking professional development opportunities that correspond with their interests and career aspirations while promoting various activities that foster professional growth without fostering obsessive tendencies. Foster a culture that values teachers' interests and hobbies outside of work and promotes activities that contribute to well-roundedness and holistic well-being. Aside from that, school administrators may incorporate reflective practices into professional development sessions to encourage teachers to regularly reflect on their teaching practices, identifying areas of growth without succumbing to obsessive tendencies. Clarify priorities and help them navigate challenges without succumbing to obsessive tendencies, thus providing guidelines on managing expectations, avoiding excessive self-imposed pressure, and establishing a supportive culture that prioritizes teachers' well-being and acknowledges the significance of an excellent work-life balance.

Undeniably, a partial mediation of moral foundation on the relationship between motivation and passion for teaching is found in this study, which can be helpful for future studies examining other variables that can mediate the relationship between variables. Besides, the research findings in this study are credible references for future researchers and educational administrative systems in the Department of Education or DepEd when planning courses and seminars for teachers.

Conclusions were derived from the study's findings. The study's data showed that the public school teachers' respondents had a high motivation and passion for teaching and a high moral foundation. The study's outcomes also demonstrated a significant association between motivation and passion for teaching. Similarly, there was a favorable relationship between motivation and moral foundation. Furthermore, a substantial relationship existed between moral foundation and passion for teaching. Moreover, the study's findings revealed that a partial mediation of moral foundation exists in the relationship between motivation and passion for teaching. Corollary to this, Deci and Ryan's (1985) Self-Determination Theory (SDT) coincided with the findings of passion for which human motivation and personality focus on people's fundamental psychological requirements and growth tendencies. It is concerned with the reasons that have driven people's decisions, regardless of whether they were affected or not by others. Self-determination theory is a macro theory of human motivation that is a fundamental component of passion and commitment, leading to effective teaching.

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